

Photocatalytic oxidation of oxalic acid over iron(III) oxide powder

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Photocatalytic oxidation of oxalic acid using iron(III) oxide powder as a photocatalyst has been investigated. The progress of the reaction was observed volumetrically. The effect of pH, concentration of oxalic acid, amount of iron(III) oxide and light intensity on the rate of the reaction has been investigated. A mechanism consistent with experimental data has been suggested.

The chemical reactions that occur in the presence of semiconductor and light are collectively termed as photocatalytic reactions. Although a lot of the work has been done on photocatalytic methods for treatment of waste waters, but negligible attention has been paid on the use of iron(III) oxide for oxidizing various organic materials. Lozano *et al.*¹ investigated the heterogeneous photocatalytic oxidation of Mn^{II} over TiO₂. Photocatalytic reduction of nitrite and nitrate ions to ammonia on Ru/TiO₂, ZnO, ZrO₂, Fe₂O₃, ZnO₂-Fe₂O₃ coupled catalysts was reported². Miyoshi *et al.*³ investigated light induced decomposition of saturated carboxylic acids on iron oxide incorporated clay suspended in aqueous solution. Water was also photocatalytically oxidized on TiO₂ coated WO₃ particles by visible light using iron(III) ions as electron acceptors⁴. Tennakone *et al.*⁵ studied oxidation of nitrogen using a composite ZnO-Fe₂O₃ catalyst. Kosanic⁶ investigated photocatalytic degradation of oxalic acid over TiO₂ powder. Preparation and characterization of γ -Fe₂O₃ semiconductor was made by Sharon and Prasad⁷.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the photocatalytic oxidation of oxalic acid was investigated. It was observed that the rate of reaction increases to an optimum value at pH 4.5, and then it decreases on increasing the pH of the medium further. The reactivity of different species related to oxalic acid decreases in the order⁸ :

In acidic medium i.e. around pH 4.0–4.5, a major fraction of oxalic acid is present in its ionic form (HC₂O₄⁻), which reacts with the photogenerated hole leading to the formation of •COOH radicals and CO₂ gas. This explains the increase in the rate of reaction up to pH 4.5. On increasing

the pH of the solution above pH 4.5, the rate of reaction decreases as fraction of the more reactive HC₂O₄⁻ species decreases and less reactive C₂O₄²⁻ increases.

Effect of concentration of oxalic acid :

Different concentrations of oxalic acid were taken. The pH of these solutions was fixed at 4.5. Fe₂O₃ (0.10 g) was added into each beaker, and it was exposed to light of intensity 60.0 mW cm⁻². The progress of the reaction was observed volumetrically with standardized potassium permanganate solution. It was observed that the rate of reaction increases with an increase in the concentration up to 1.0 × 10⁻³ M. This may be due to the fact that as the concentration of the acid was increased, more molecules were available for excitation and consecutive energy transfer. As a result, there was an increase in the rate of reaction. The rate of reaction however decreased on increasing the concentration of oxalic acid further. This may be due to the fact that on further increasing the concentration of oxalic acid, its movement is hindered by the molecules themselves and the oxalic acid molecules do not reach the semiconductor surface in the desired time limit, hence a decrease in the rate of the reaction was observed.

Effect of amount of iron(III) oxide powder :

Various amounts of iron(III) oxide powder ranging from 0.02 to 0.10 g were added to the solutions of oxalic acid and were exposed to light. Large amounts of iron(III) oxide i.e. above 0.10 g could not be used as slight light yellow colour appeared in the oxalic acid solution during the reaction. The appearance of light yellow colour in the solution of oxalic acid might be due to consumption of some iron(III) oxide powder, which creates problems in measurement. It was observed that the value of rate constant increases with an increase in the amount of iron(III) oxide powder, which may be attributed to the fact that as the amount of semiconductor was increased, the exposed surface area also increases,

whereby increasing the rate of the reaction.

Effect of intensity of light :

The solution of oxalic acid was exposed to light of different intensities ranging from 10.0 to 80.0 mW cm⁻². It was observed that, the rate of the reaction increases with an increase in the intensity of light. This may be explained by the fact that on increasing the light intensity, the number of photons striking per unit area of iron(III) oxide powder also increases.

Mechanism :

On the basis of observations, a tentative mechanism for photocatalytic oxidation of oxalic acid to carbon dioxide, over iron(III) oxide may be proposed as follows :

The amount of carbon dioxide evolved increases with an increase in oxalic acid concentration up to a certain limit. Oxygen reacts effectively with photoelectrons forming $O_2^{\bullet -}$ or $\bullet HO_2$ radicals, and it may inhibit the electron-hole recombination.

$\bullet COOH$ free radical formed disappears by reaction with O_2 and generates $\bullet HO_2$ radicals

Ordinarily, recombination of $\bullet HO_2$ leads to the formation of H_2O_2

but H_2O_2 was not found to be the final product, hence it may be concluded that H_2O_2 was consumed during photo-oxidation⁹.

Experimental

0.0158 g of oxalic acid (B.D.H.) was dissolved in 250 ml of double-distilled water so that the concentration of oxalic acid was $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. 50.0 ml of the oxalic acid solution was taken in a beaker and 0.10 g of iron(III) oxide powder (Reidel) was added to it. The pH of the solution was adjusted by addition of previously standardized solution of sodium hydroxide, and pH was measured by a digital pH meter (Systronics 335). The solution of oxalic acid was then exposed to light (intensity 40.0 mW cm^{-2}), which was measured by a solarimeter (Surya Mapi CEL 201). After a fixed time interval, 3.0 ml of oxalic acid solution was taken out and it was titrated against standardized potassium permanganate ($3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) to monitor the progress of the reaction.

The plot of $1 + \log \text{O.D.}$ vs time was a straight line, which indicates that the photocatalytic oxidation of oxalic acid follows pseudo first order kinetics. The rate constant k for the reaction was determined using the expression $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$.

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